

What is the role of Social Life Cycle Assessment within the context of Safe and Sustainable-by-Design? An explorative study

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Keywords (3-8): social assessment, safe and sustainable by design, circular, integration approach

ABSTRACT

The European Green Deal (EC, 2019) aims to shift the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in effective actions in order to achieve a sustainable, climate-neutral, and circular vision of Europe by 2050. The main purpose is to protect human health and the environment by pollution from all sources to promote a free-toxic economy (EC, 2021). The European Chemical Strategy (EC, 2020) for Sustainability and the Zero Pollution Action Plan (EC, 2021) identify pollution as a key driver of planetary crises as well as highlight the hazardous properties of chemical materials and substances (Caldeira et al., 2022, Fantke et al., 2022) for human health. Investments in designing, manufacturing and utilizing more sustainable chemistries, materials, and products are needed to facilitate the green transition of the economy. Safety and Sustainability-by-Design (SSbD) is a central element of the European Chemical Strategy (EC, 2020) aiming to minimize exposure to substances and other concerning stressors for human health and/or the environment, whilst also promoting their substitution (e.g., sustainable bio-based chemicals) with advanced materials and better alternatives. In this context, a framework for the definition of SSbD criteria for chemicals and materials was developed by the Joint Research Center (JRC) which included also a description of the criteria to be addressed (Caldeira et al., 2022). The SSbD encourages the holistic approach of Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) for considering a full life cycle perspective (i.e., from the raw material extraction phase to the end-of-life management phase) of products and/or services (ISO 14040/44:2021) and/or organizations (ISO 14072:2014; UNEP, 2015). Among the LCT tools, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) assesses the environmental impacts of products and services; Life Cycle Costing (LCC) analyses the costs derived from the life cycle of the analyzed product and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) assesses the social and socio-economic aspects linked to the life cycle of analysed products. Additionally, Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) integrates the evaluation of three dimensions of sustainability. Recently, ORIENTING Project funded by EU Horizon 2020 developed an operational methodology for promoting this integration by also considering the elements of Criticality and Circularity. Even though human health and human well-being play a crucial role in achieving the vision of Europe in 2050, the social aspects are the less assessed both at academic and industrial levels. S-LCA is a methodology that assesses potential social impacts (in terms of social performance and/or social risks), negative and positive, of products and services from a life cycle perspective. It is recognized that S-LCA can be used as a decision-making support tool (Petti et al., 2018) allowing an evaluation of performance, risk, and potential impact levels. It follows the technical framework of ISO 14040:2021 and ISO 14044:2021 as well as the Guidelines for Social LCA, recently revised (i.e., UNEP, 2020), compared to the previous version (i.e., UNEP/SETAC, 2009). Even though the standardization process is currently underway (i.e., ISO/FDIS 14075), a shared consensus on S-LCA applications has not yet been reached (Tsalis et al., 2017; D'Eusanio et al., 2020; Huertas-Valdivia et al. 2020). Several criticalities on the S-LCA methodology (e.g., common consensus on social indicators, the way to allocate impacts to each involved process (Grubert, 2018), how to measure them and how to identify relevant stakeholder categories and social topics (Tragnone et al., 2022), data quality and its representativeness) are still at stake. S-LCA is characterized by a context-specific assessment where the collected data mainly concern the analyzed context and the behavior of the companies involved in the life cycle of the product. S-LCA is based on a stakeholder approach (UNEP, 2020), in which they are affected by the behavior of organizations, and they can also affect the decision-making process related to the life cycle of the products. ANALYST Project funded by EU Horizon aims to develop an integrated approach for a holistic health, environmental, social, and economic impact assessment of the plastic value chain.

In this context, it is important to understand the role of S-LCA within the SSbD framework and how the EU Projects addressed it. In particular, this study aims to investigate how the social dimension of the EU Projects on SSbD has been addressed; 2) whether and how S-LCA methodology has been implemented. Moreover, it aims to understand how circularity and social aspects have been integrated in order for them to be addressed in a holistic way. The findings show that not all the EU projects on SSbD have focused on social aspects, even though some of them are attentive to the hazard risk assessment that can be linked to the social topics of Health and Safety both for the workers and consumers stakeholder categories. Moreover, S-LCA can be differently implemented at methodological levels and different impact assessment methods could be followed. S-LCA can be a decision-making support tool for designing more sustainable and safe products. Indeed, it allows for identifying the social risk and/or social performance related to specific chemical materials and substances involved in the life cycle of analyzed products. Furthermore, the S-LCA results enable supporting the management of the entire value chain of the product from the suppliers to the end user from a social perspective.

Acknowledgments and Disclaimers

This study was financially supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101138548 (ANALYST). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union and of the Consortium Partners of ANALYST Project. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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